

HIGH-P METAHYALOCLASTITES FROM THE SOMOZAS MÉLANGE (CABO ORTEGAL COMPLEX, NW IBERIA): TECTONIC IMPLICATIONS FOR THE ASSEMBLY OF PANGAEA

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In the lowest structural position of the Cabo Ortegal Complex (NW Iberian Massif), the Somozas Mélange represents a typical serpentinitic mélange interpreted as a Variscan suture zone. It contains different types of tectonic blocks wrapped by a serpentinitic matrix. In the locality of Espasante, exposures along the coast give access to a distinctive and unique tectonic within the mélange. The block is constituted by submarine metavolcanic rocks with broken pillow breccias, close-packed pillow lavas, hyaloclastites, basaltic andesites and doleritic dykes. The basaltic andesites show typical calc-alkaline composition but the geochemistry of the doleritic dykes indicates arc-tholeiitic affinity. The age of the volcanic rocks is unknown, but their origin has been related to the activity of a Cambrian peri-Gondwanan magmatic arc. The andesitic rocks were probably formed during convergent activity in the arc, while the tholeiitic rocks indicate incorporation of juvenile magmas during an evolving dynamic setting. The metahyaloclastitic matrix of the pillow breccias is the rock studied in this work. It shows a first hydrothermal metamorphism that strongly modified its initial chemical composition, and favored the development of a second recrystallization event.

The second metamorphic event developed a complex high-P mineral assemblage formed by muscovite-paragonite-margarite-quartz-garnet-kyanite-chlorite-epidote-hematite-rutile, with apatite and tourmaline as accessory phases. Pseudosection modelling in the MnCNTKFMASHO system indicates metamorphic peak conditions at 17.5-18 kbar and 550°C, followed by drastic decompression with minor temperature decrease. This P-T evolution demonstrates an initial subduction event for a slab including the submarine volcanic rocks, followed by fast exhumation as a tectonic block incorporated to the subduction channel represented by the serpentinitic mélange. In this context, the Somozas Mélange represents a major tectonic boundary within the Variscan Orogen.

Keywords: High-P metamorphism, Metahyaloclastites of the Somozas Mélange, Cabo Ortegal Complex (NW Iberian Massif, Variscan Orogen).